

Kinetic Study of Solvent Effect on Alkali catalysed Hydrolysis of Dimethyl Phthalate in Aquo-dioxane, Aquo-acetone and Aquo-DMSO Media

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A kinetic study of solvent effect on alkali-catalysed hydrolysis of dimethyl phthalate has been made in aquo-dioxane, aquo-acetone and aquo-DMSO solvent mixtures at different temperatures. The first dissociation constant value, evaluated by the method of French, was found to decrease with increasing amount of the organic co-solvent in the media like aquo-dioxane and aquo-acetone, while the same enhances in aquo-DMSO. The variation in rate as well as the activation parameters have been interpreted on the basis of specific solvation and the dielectric properties of the medium. The polarisation energy has been evaluated to test the polarisibility of the transition state.

A good amount of work has been carried out to correlate the rate change with the nature and properties of the solvent medium and striking results have been obtained. Predictions of Hughes and Ingold¹ and Laidler and Landskroener² that in a system of increasing dielectric constant, the rate of a reaction is expected to rise. However, in many instances, Parker³ and Roberts⁴ found the rate constant values decreasing under similar condition of increasing dielectric constant in the medium. In this study of solvent effect on the alkaline hydrolysis of dimethyl phthalate (which hydrolyses in two steps) an attempt has been made to investigate the effect in different solvent media such as aquo-dioxane, aquo-acetone and aquo-DMSO (in variable amount of the organic solvent) at different temperatures with a view to see as to how these predictions are applicable in this particular reaction. Further, the nature of the transition state regarding their polarisibility has also been investigated by evaluating the recently proposed function known as molar Polarisation energy change.

Experimental

Reaction mixtures were prepared using varying amounts of purified organic solvent and water. Double-distilled water was used. A 0.5 M NaOH was used. The reaction mixture was kept thermostated for 0.5 h and weighed amount of the ester was added to it. Aliquots (5 ml) removed at different intervals of time, were estimated titrimetrically. First and second order rate constants (k_1 and k_2) were calculated using the equation of French⁵. Only k_1 values (Tables 1-3) were considered for solvent effect discussion as k_2 values were more than ten times that of the k_1 values.

TABLE 1— $k_1 (\times 10^2)$ VALUES OF ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF DIMETHYL PHTHALATE IN DIOXANE-WATER MEDIUM

Temp °C	Composition of dioxane (% v/v)				
	30	40	50	60	70
20	23.4	19.9	17.0	15.1	13.5
25	28.4	24.0	21.9	18.6	16.2
30	31.6	28.2	24.0	22.4	20.0
35	33.9	31.6	28.2	26.3	24.6

TABLE 2— $k_1 (\times 10^2)$ VALUES OF ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF DIMETHYL PHTHALATE IN ACETONE-WATER MEDIUM

Temp. °C	Composition of acetone (% v/v)				
	30	40	50	60	70
20	39.8	37.4	30.9	27.8	24.5
25	51.3	44.7	39.8	35.5	30.2
30	61.6	52.5	49.0	41.6	37.1
35	74.1	66.1	57.5	52.5	42.6

TABLE 3— $k_1 (\times 10^3)$ VALUES OF ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF DIMETHYL PHTHALATE IN DMSO-WATER MEDIUM

Temp °C	Composition of DMSO (% v/v)				
	30	40	50	60	70
20	28.3	36.4	39.2	42.2	57.9
25	37.7	48.7	52.3	58.2	70.0
30	52.5	60.7	65.0	74.1	85.7
35	67.3	79.0	82.0	90.4	97.7

Results and Discussions

Tables 1 and 2 show a decrease in rate constant values with increasing proportion of dioxane and acetone respectively, in the media. These decreasing trends are in accordance with the reported views^{1,2,6} which account for the preferred formation of more polar transition state in the medium of high dielectric constant. But the phenomenon of

solvation plays more important role in aquo-dioxane medium. Dioxane has two lone-pairs and thereby has a tendency for hydrogen bonding with a number of water molecules. Hence, dioxane by its considerable entrance in secondary solvation sheath of OH⁻ ion, will contribute to its greater solvation. In aquo-acetone system, the decrease in rate is not as steep as in aquo-dioxane. Hence both the factors, i.e. solvation and dielectric changes appear to act simultaneously in affecting the rate of reaction. But the rate constant (Table 3) increases with the increasing amount of DMSO in the medium. This can be interpreted on the basis of poor anion solvating property of DMSO. The reactant OH⁻ ion is likely to be more and more desolvated with increasing proportion of DMSO in the mixture. This will result lowering of activation energy and hence an increase in the rate constant values. This observation is in tune with that expressed by Parker³ and Roberts⁴.

Using the Arrhenius law, the iso-composition activation energy (E_c) values were calculated from the plots of $\log k_1$ vs $1/T$ (Table 4). Other activation parameters such as ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* were

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION ENERGY VALUES (E_c , kJ mol⁻¹) OF HYDROLYSIS IN DIFFERENT ORGANIC SOLVENT MIXTURES

Solvent	Composition of organic solvent (% v/v)				
	30	40	50	60	70
Aquo-dioxane	19.7	22.2	26.1	31.1	32.9
Aquo-acetone	34.6	30.2	28.0	26.1	25.5
Aquo-DMSO	45.3	39.9	35.1	31.7	26.2

also evaluated for all the solvent media. Since the ΔG^* values are almost constant throughout the range of a solvent system, they have not been recorded here. The other parameters are shown in Table 5. The E_c or ΔH^* values increase in aquo-dioxane and decrease in aquo-DMSO with the added

TABLE 5— ΔH^* (kJ mol⁻¹) AND ΔS^* (JK mol⁻¹) VALUES OF THE REACTION IN DIFFERENT SOLVENT MIXTURES

Solvent mixture	Composition of organic solvent (% v/v)				
	30	40	50	60	70
Aquo-dioxane					
ΔH^*	17.9	20.4	23.0	28.9	32.9
ΔS^*	-229.8	-222.5	-215.2	-196.4	-188.2
Aquo-acetone					
ΔH^*	31.5	27.7	25.5	23.8	22.9
ΔS^*	-178.5	-192.7	-200.6	-207.6	-211.4
Aquo-DMSO					
ΔH^*	40.8	35.8	33.0	30.3	22.8
ΔS^*	-149.4	-164.7	-173.5	-181.3	-204.9

organic solvent in the medium. The trends are normal as the rate decreases in the former and increases in the latter medium. In aquo-acetone however, the E_c or ΔH^* values were found to decrease which should have favoured an enhancement in rate. This unusual behaviour in the solvent system is due to increase in ΔS^* with increasing

proportion of acetone in the solvent mixture. The ΔH^* and ΔS^* variations obey Barclay-Butler rule⁷ in all the solvent mixtures and the isokinetic temperatures are within the range of 250–400 suggesting⁸ solvation changes without any change in the usual mechanism.

Molar polarisation energy change: Recently, the following relationship has been proposed^{9,10} for the molar polarisation energy change $N\Sigma Ge^2/b^3$ for ester hydrolysis,

$$N\Sigma Ge^2/b^3 = 4.094 RTA(1-1/D) - 1.8 E_D$$

where E_D is the isodielectric activation energy, A the slope of $\log k_1$ against $1/D$, N the Avogadro number and G the number which expresses the distribution of charges on a spherical molecule. The summation stands for the sum of the properties of reactants and transition states. The positive sign of the molar polarisation energy indicates that the initial state is more polarised than the transition state while the negative value indicates the opposite trend. The $N\Sigma Ge^2/b^3$ values in all the solvent systems are shown in Table 6. In all the solvent

TABLE 6—MOLAR POLARISATION ENERGY CHANGE IN HYDROLYSIS REACTION IN DIFFERENT SOLVENT SYSTEMS

Temp. K	Solvent mixture	A	100/D	E_D kJ mol ⁻¹	D	$N\Sigma Ge^2/b^3$ kJ mol ⁻¹
303	Aquo-dioxane	109.0	2.0	23.6	50.0	-1144.1
303	Aquo-acetone	351.1	2.1	30.9	47.0	-3596.8
303	Aquo-DMSO	66.7	1.47	3.6	68.0	-671.3

media only negative values have been obtained, suggesting the transition states being more polarised than the initial states. This also means that the bond-breaking processes precede the bond-forming processes in all the media.

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